

Tactile tuning after object manipulation with unreliable tactile feedback

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Abstract. Sensory systems are adaptable to change. For instance, in the visual system, this is reflected in enhanced sensitivity of an eye that was visually deprived or had received unreliable information. But does that also apply to the tactile sensory system? We hypothesized that providing unreliable somatosensory information on the one hand leads to enhanced tactile perception. Participants performed a brief tactile discrimination task during which stimuli were presented on their index fingers, with the left finger receiving a reference stimulus. Following this baseline measure, participants performed a 60-minute intervention, during which they performed building tasks with small blocks only using their right hand while wearing a thick glove. Their left hand did not participate in the task. Right after the intervention, we re-tested tactile sensitivity. Our data showed enhanced tactile sensitivity on the right hand during the first four minutes after the intervention, an effect that vanished afterward. These findings suggest that the human tactile system shows a degree of adaptability.

Keywords: tactile perception, sensory tuning, tactile tuning

1 Introduction

Our sensory systems are adaptable. For example, shortly after the visual system is deprived of or provided with unreliable visual information (i.e. delayed information), its sensitivity changes as it becomes more enhanced [1, 2]. We are interested in testing whether depriving tactile information from healthy participants will lead to enhanced tactile sensitivity. We expect that tactile sensitivity on a limb will be enhanced after this limb is deprived of or provided with unreliable tactile information.

2 Methods

2.1 Participants

Eighteen right-handed participants (18-35 years old; 11 females) joined the experiment. All participants were right-handed according to the German translation of the Edinburgh Handedness Inventory, with normal vision and no neurological or orthopedical conditions affecting sensorimotor processes of the limbs. Participants provided their

signed informed consent according to the Declaration of Helsinki (2013; except §35, pre-registration) and were compensated with 8 €/hour or credit points.

2.2 Apparatus, Stimuli & Protocol

At the beginning of the experiment, participants performed a short discrimination task. Two vibrotactile devices (tactors) (Engineering Acoustics, TX, USA) were attached to each of the participant's index fingerpads, delivering brief vibrotactile stimuli (50 ms, 250 Hz). The peak-to-peak displacement of the stimuli on the right hand (test stimuli) varied between 16 and 300 μm in steps of 47 μm , while that of the stimuli on the left hand was constant at 160 μm . Participants received tactile stimuli in both hands simultaneously and reported which of the two felt stronger by pressing the respective foot pedal. Participants wore earplugs during the measurement. An intervention followed this baseline tactile sensitivity test, during which participants built Duplo and Lego constructions for one hour (30 minutes each) while wearing a ski glove on their right hand. The left hand did not participate in the task. Participants were only allowed to use their index finger and thumb while completing the building blocks. With the completion of the 60 minutes, a procedure identical to the first, but more extended, consisting of 5 blocks, each covering a single epoch, followed to assess the effects of the intervention on tactile sensitivity. Each of the six tactile sensitivity blocks (1 pre-intervention, 5 post-intervention) lasted ~ 2 minutes, and the experiment lasted in total ~ 90 minutes.

2.3 Analysis

We fit the responses to the stimuli with separate psychometric functions for each tactile sensitivity test using `psignifit 4` [3] in Matlab 2022 (MATLAB R2022b, The MathWorks Inc). We then estimated the point of subjective equality (PSE) of each function, for each participant. To quantify the effect of the intervention on tactile sensitivity, we subtracted each participant's pre-intervention PSE from each of their five post-intervention PSEs, with positive values indicating enhanced sensitivity after the intervention. To evaluate any effects of the intervention on tactile sensitivity, we tested the resulting values against zero (i.e. pre-intervention sensitivity) using five one-sample t -tests, corrected with the Bonferroni-Holm procedure for multiple comparisons.

3 Results

The data of the average tactile modulation across participants are shown in Figure 1, where it becomes clear that tactile sensitivity improves during the first two epochs after the intervention. This was supported by a statistically significant enhancement during the first ($t_{17} = 3.00$, $p = 0.03$) and second ($t_{17} = 3.10$, $p = 0.03$) blocks after the intervention, which did not occur in the subsequent blocks (all $t < 1.06$, all $p > 0.76$).

Fig. 1. Group average, with the baseline set from the pre-test phase to zero. Error bars represent standard error of the mean. The x-axis represents the blocks (~2 mins) and y-axis the change from baseline (horizontal line). Grey lines indicate different participants. The red colors show the fading post-intervention effect.

4 Discussion

We explored whether the tactile system adapts after performing a manual task with unreliable tactile information. We found enhanced tactile sensitivity during the first four minutes after performing such a task, an effect that quickly disappeared. This suggests that the tactile system is adaptable, and when deprived of receiving information its sensitivity increases, but unlike the other sensory systems, the effects appear rather short lasting. This improved sensitivity may also arise due to the intervention requiring continuous sampling of tactile information or increasing the temperature of the tested hand, both of which may subsequently enhance tactile sensitivity. In future work we shall address the possibility of the reference hand's influence (e.g., suppression), for instance by involving it to the task, with or without the use of a glove.

Acknowledgments. This work was supported by the Collaborative Research Center SFB/TRR 135, project A4, under grant agreement 222641018 funded by the German Research Institute (Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft), and by “The Adaptive Mind” funded by the Hessian Ministry for Higher Education, Research, Science 437 and the Arts.

Disclosure of Interests. The authors have declared no competing interest.

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